

Regulatory Push for Circularity: The Impact of EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17621367](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17621367)

KEYWORDS

Circular economy,
EU textile strategy,
Sustainable
fashion,
Extended Producer
Responsibility
(EPR),
Eco-design
regulation

ABSTRACT

The textile industry is one of the most resource-intensive and polluting sectors globally, driven by fast fashion and a linear production model that relies heavily on virgin materials and generates excessive waste. In response to the mounting environmental and social challenges, the European Union has introduced new Strategies toward Sustainable and Circular Textiles to accelerate the industry's transition toward circularity. This review examines the regulatory instruments, policy frameworks, and strategic initiatives—like the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), and Digital Product Passports—that aim to reduce environmental impacts, promote recycling, and encourage product longevity. It also explores the alignment of the EU strategy with broader sustainability goals, including the European Green Deal and global climate agreements. The study highlights both the transformative potential and implementation challenges of circular policies in the textile supply chain, emphasizing the need for multi-stakeholder collaboration, consumer responsibility, and supportive infrastructure. The paper concludes that regulatory frameworks play a pivotal role in reshaping the future of textiles and fostering a sustainable, closed-loop economy.

1. INTRODUCTION

With 100 billion garments produced annually, the textile sector has expanded significantly over the last few decades to rank among the biggest in the world. A significant contributor to this enormous production is the fast fashion phenomenon, which employs 60% of the world's fiber production and is distinguished by its low costs and quick turnover. The creation

of clothing hurts the environment. Each year about 5 million tons of greenhouse gases are produced from fashion industry, accounting for 8–10% of worldwide CO₂ emissions. It amalgamates about 2.5% of the world's total agriculturally usable land for cotton production, is the second-largest consumer of freshwater in the world (79 trillion liters annually, with that amount predicted to rise by 50% within 2030), and contributes 20% to industrial water

pollution (1). Another notorious aspect of the textile business is the serious chemical contamination it produces. Eight million tons of fertilizer and sixteen thousand tons of pesticides are used yearly in cotton cultivation alone, and numerous additional chemicals (figure 1) are employed along the production chain. Each year, in amount, 92 million tons of textile waste are produced worldwide. According to future estimates, it is also estimated that the amount of textile waste could reach around 150 million tons by 2050 if everything continued as it is. Furthermore, the textile sector may consume slightly less than 27% of carbon budget linked to the 2 °C rise of global temperatures by 2050 (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017). Therefore, it is indisputable that structural reforms are required because this business strategy is currently unsustainable. The shift to a more circular textile sector is one suggested lever to address this problem (2, 3).

In order to maintain materials flowing like nutrients rather than being wasted, ongoing horizontal flow of materials needs to be changed. Product and process should be made to produce closed-loop systems. Although recycling and reusing textiles are thought to be more environmentally friendly than landfilling or incineration, there are obstacles in the textile industry that restrict recycling. The Circular

Economy (CE) is a technique that reduces waste and adverse environmental effects by reusing, recycling, and remanufacturing materials in supply chain operations to create circular models (1). By increasing the life cycle of products and keeping their value at its highest level for as long as feasible inside the value chain, the circular economy focuses mainly on the total value chain and wants to reduce the use of virgin resources. The European Union (EU) and the United Nations, in particular, actively encourage circularity for the textile business (2). Manufacturing waste and obstacles to sustainable business models can be significantly reduced by implementing CE techniques. 2017 research titled "Make Fashion Circular" written by Ellen MacArthur Foundation found that the fast-fashion industry has expanded dramatically, leading to the yearly ended up of 48 million tons of clothing worldwide. These numbers are increasing and are expected to increase significantly, mostly due to the Waste Framework Directive's implementation (figure 2). The directive represents the immediate need to fix this concerning environmental impact of the fashion industry and promote ecologically friendly ways for the production and ending up of apparels by mandating the individual collection of textile waste from other garbage by 2025.

Figure 1: Key steps in the textile manufacturing process, along with examples of the chemicals employed at each stage (2).

Figure 2: Waste hierarchy concept (Waste framework directive 2008) (4).

To promote circular and sustainable textile production, regulations are essential. These are similar to strong instruments that offer direction, establish criteria, and encourage companies to use ecologically and socially conscious practices. Both the supply and demand sides of the circular economy (CE) must be addressed by effective laws and policies. Investment in ecologically friendly initiatives, or "green finance," is essential on the supply side. A successful transition to a CE requires converting conventional business models to circular business models. To encourage more investment in the CE,

2. Urgency of Regulatory Push for Circularity

The textile industry uses more than 15,000 chemicals now, including over 5000 auxiliary chemicals and more than 10,000 dyes and pigments. According to estimates, 0.58 kg of different types of chemicals are needed to bring 1 kg of textile material, meaning that 43 million tons of chemicals are used on yearly basis. In addition to the enormous quantity of chemicals used in textile production, it is highly challenging to monitor chemical usage across the entire production chain due to the textile value chain's global diversity. The value chain

policy-makers should concentrate on the difficulties in luring capital and guaranteeing the initiatives' financial viability. Policy-makers should increase the appeal of circular materials to consumers, particularly those who are older, less educated, and from higher-income groups, to meet demand. Circular practices can be promoted through fiscal policy incentives. Policy-makers in the future should examine how these consumer incentives affect the adoption of sustainable practices according to CE standards (1).

does, in fact, include a wide range of players and stakeholders, and the various production phases are conducted in many nations and areas across the globe. It can be extremely challenging for downstream producers to determine where and how their materials have been treated because of the geographical dispersion of the many production steps and the disparate national laws pertaining to the use of chemicals. Poor knowledge about the presence of chemicals in finished goods is the result of cumulative ignorance along the textile production chain, and it is impossible to rule out the presence of hazardous materials. To better protect the health of people and the environment, chemical use regulations have undergone major changes

in recent years, and additional changes are anticipated in the years to come (2, 5). A visual contrast of linear model and circular economy model has been depicted in figure 3.

For instance, the EU took a significant step in 2006 when the REACH rules and regulations (Regulation EC No. 1907/2006) on the Registration, Evaluation, and Authorization of different kinds of Chemicals were imbibed. A safer use of chemicals is the purpose of the EU Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, which was passed in 2020 and has objectives through

2050. Reusing textiles made before protective laws were put in place, however, can keep dangerous materials in the textile supply chain. In fact, there have been concerns expressed about the (in)ability of the existing standards to offer adequate protection with relation to recirculating materials (2).

Figure 3: Contrast between linear and circular model of economy (6).

3. Relevant Law and Policy Structures

- **Environmental Regulations and Sustainability Standards (ERSS)**

Environmental regulation is necessary to shift economies away from the traditional linear paradigm of the extraction, manufacture, consumption, and waste processes. Strong economic and social goals should guide its creation, and it should target specific groups like the elderly, the less educated, and the wealthy. New items should be made to last and planned obsolescence should be outlawed in

order to encourage sustainability. Customers may be able to identify products with recycled inputs by using product tags or QR codes that indicate the level of sustainability. Environmental sensitivity may be promoted by higher tariffs on goods made entirely of basic raw materials. Conversely, lower value-added taxes could be advantageous for goods with high sustainability levels. Targeted taxes and stringent regulations might affect the market's supply and demand (7).

- **The UN Climate Agreements**

Climate change international agreements: In 1992, the United States and 179 other countries signed the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), which was the first to address climate change. To stabilize the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, they held conferences. Additionally, it resulted in the Kyoto Protocol in 2005 and the Paris Agreement in 2015, which sought to manage global temperatures and achieve net-zero emissions, respectively, while requiring wealthy nations to reduce emissions without requiring action from underdeveloped nations (8).

- **Kyoto Protocol**

Adopted on 11th December, 1997, the Kyoto Protocol came into rule on February 16, 2005 with the goal and vision of this worldwide agreement is to lower greenhouse gas emissions that contribute to global warming. For the stability of GHG emissions targets, it had two commitment periods. 2008–2012 was the first-time frame, while 2013–2020 was the second.

- **Paris Agreement**

4. EU Textile Sustainability and Circularity Strategy

The European Commission estimates that each year, the average European wastes away 11 kilograms of textile waste. These discarded textiles end up in landfills, which harm the environment, energy, water, and resources. To address these issues, the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles offered a number of solutions. This approach outlines sustainable options for textile consumption, creative business strategies, and their effects on the environment. Due to these regulations, textile manufacturers must employ a specific percentage of recycled materials in

The goal of the Paris Climate Agreement, which was ratified on December 12, 2015, and went into effect on November 4, 2016, is to further cut greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and lower global temperatures by 2 °C this century.

- **European Green Deal**

European Green Deal got a formal introduction on December 2019 with keeping the ultimate objective of becoming carbon (C) neutral by the end of 2050. This was unveiled with a comprehensive plan to direct the smooth transition to a greener future. It highlights how important it is to handle climate-related issues through a coordinated, cross-sectoral approach in which several policy areas work together. The interdependence of the domains of climate, environment, energy, transportation, industry, agriculture, and sustainable finance is acknowledged by this endeavor (9).

- **European Climate Law**

This law initiates that the European Union will become carbon neutral by 2050. It includes the EU and its member working together to lessen their greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% from 1990 levels by 2030.

their products. They also stress the product's durability and ease of repair. Furthermore, the final product must be recyclable. Some of the measures undertaken by the EU for the implementation of sustainable and circular textiles are given below (1):

1. The Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)
2. Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)
3. Producer responsibility
4. Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Change
5. Digital product passports
6. Action Plan-2020

7. Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
8. Alliance for Sustainable Fashion
9. Responsibilities of consumers.
10. Textiles-2030

The Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)

The proposed Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation, one of the regulatory proposals made official by the European Commission, lays out a framework to enhance product circularity by incorporating a digital product passport that could store data like durability and repairability, making recycling or repair easier, and making it easier to track problematic substances throughout the supply chain. In the future, it might specify the amount of recycled yarn used in a garment and highlight materials that could make a product non-recyclable. Additionally, the law would mandate that businesses disclose to the public any unsold product destruction. Guidelines to prevent the inadvertent discharge of microplastics from textiles and to guarantee the veracity of environmental claims by encouraging circular business models will also be part of

the specific measures (10).

Although the eco-design regulations enacted under the ESPR would seem to be uniform across the EU, each member state would determine its penalties, which would lead to variations in the severity of the enforcement of the law. Specific product standards would only be outlined in secondary legislation following the implementation of the ESPR, at which point goods that do not meet the requirements would be prohibited from

Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Change

achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 and the pressing need to combat climate change were both highlighted in the 2018 IPCC report. In order to create a coordinated climate action plan, the UN Climate Change is spearheading

being sold on the EU market. The way clothing is designed and made is probably going to be significantly impacted if the legislation continues in this direction.

Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)

Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), which builds on the idea of waste management and environmental degradation, is viewed by European environmental policy as a community-level innovation that pushes businesses to create more recyclable and sustainable goods and production methods. This is the path that businesses will take in order to become more environmentally conscious and to shift the cost of sustainability—from procuring raw materials to end-of-life and recycling—from local governments to manufacturers. All of this is meant to help the contemporary maker better predict the constantly shifting needs for compliance (10). A schematic diagram in figure 4 shows the intervention points for successful implementation of this tool.

Producer responsibility

There will be new regulations requiring textile manufacturers to assume greater responsibility for product design in order to increase the durability of clothing. In order to identify better ways to create clothing with fewer resources and to promote activities like repairing and recycling clothing rather than throwing it away, the Commission will involve many stakeholders in circular business models. Additionally, it recommends that Member States provide assistance and tax breaks to companies that encourage clothing repair and reuse (5).

The fashion industry's responsibility to support the Paris Agreement's goals of

efforts to unite all parties involved in the fashion industry, from businesses to those who provide the raw materials. This program is supposed to define innovative projects and develop current ones across the fashion value.

In doing so, it is assumed that it would, by default, address climate change effectively (11).

Digital product passports

Digital product passport and transparent textile info are required to disclose the pertinent data on sustainability and other environmental aspects. Greenwashing, which is the practice of

Figure 4: A product's life cycle and potential EPR instrument intervention locations are shown schematically (4).

businesses making embroidered or deceptive claims to be environmentally friendly, is strictly regulated under these tactics. It helps shield customers from being conned. This tactic is also beneficial for future Green Claims Initiatives, which will supposedly assist businesses that make environmentally friendly claims to be sincere (7).

Action Plan 2020

Between 2012 and 2020, the Sustainable Clothing Action Plan, which united textile recyclers, charity shops, and UK fashion retailers, made significant progress. The WRAP (Waste & Resources Action Program)-led, industry-driven

project yielded significant financial and environmental benefits. Their targets are to cut waste from refilling by 15%, cut carbon and water footprints by 15%, and cut waste from the product's whole lifecycle by 3.5%. WRAP significantly decreased the carbon footprint, water consumption, and waste related to clothes by promoting cooperation, directing improvement initiatives, establishing goals, monitoring advancement, and exchanging experiences. Throughout its nine-year journey, SCAP cemented its position as a pioneer in sustainable fashion by giving businesses of all sizes the knowledge and resources they need to transform the textile industry (1).

Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism

One of the significant mechanisms which is used by the EU to try to charge a fair price for the carbon emissions produced during the production of carbon-intensive goods that are imported into the EU is the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). The primary goal is to encourage industrial output in non-EU nations to be cleaner and more sustainable. In addition to this, the progressive implementation of the CBAM, the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) will reduce the free allowances granted to EU industry. The EU's initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and boost the decarbonization of its businesses are supported by this change.

Beginning on October 1, 2023, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) will go into operation during a transitional period. It will first be used for particular products and raw materials that are very susceptible to carbon leakage and have carbon-intensive production methods. These consist of hydrogen, fertilizers, iron and steel, aluminum, cement, and electricity. Over 50% of emissions in industries presently covered by the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) will be covered by the CBAM when it is progressively implemented. The goal of this transitional phase is to collect useful data on embedded emissions while also piloting and learning from the implementation with importers, manufacturers, and regulators (12).

Alliance for Sustainable Fashion

To collaborate on sustainable development goals in the fashion industry, the UN established the United Nations Alliance for Sustainable Fashion in 2019. Paris, which aims to become a sustainable fashion capital by 2024, and Stockholm, which canceled Fashion Week to find eco-friendly alternatives, were two cities that were already supporting this idea. In order to promote sustainable fashion globally, numerous nations have also started a variety of national programs. The list illustrates the variety of initiatives in this expanding field, but it is not all-inclusive.

The various steps of production in a circular economy are used to map the initiatives and rules, demonstrating how well each one contributes to sustainability (13).

The United Nations Alliance for Sustainable Fashion was established by UN agencies and allied groups to promote the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the fashion sector. This project addresses a number of fashion-related topics, such as raw materials, production, distribution, use, and disposal. It aims for sustainability by tackling social and environmental problems like trash reduction and greenhouse gas emissions, as well as social ones like equitable working conditions. The Alliance's ultimate goal is to use the fashion industry to decrease its negative effects, encourage positive change, and assist in achieving the SDGs (14).

Consumer responsibility

For consumers, this new textile strategy aims to shift purchasing behaviors by promoting higher-quality, longer-lasting garments and encouraging practices like repairing and reusing clothing instead of discarding them. To support this transition, the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform will collaborate with key players—including designers, manufacturers, retailers, advertisers, and the public—to redefine the fashion industry in the EU. The goal is to foster a more sustainable and ethical approach to fashion, moving away from disposable trends and toward a system that prioritizes durability, reuse, and environmental responsibility (5).

Textiles 2030

In the groundbreaking initiative Textiles 2030, leading sustainability experts from the UK fashion and textiles sectors have joined the Waste & Resources Action Program (WRAP). Its goal is to encourage this industry to move toward a circular economy, where items are recycled and utilized again. It is a voluntary

agreement backed by funding from the government and participating organizations rather than a strict mandate. The signatories promise to work together to combat climate change, conserve water, and promote circular textiles. They have the power to affect textile policies in the UK. This plan serves as the foundation for the Sustainable Clothing Action Plan (SCAP 2020), which aims to involve most UK fashion and textile industries in cooperative, climate-friendly projects (1, 2).

5. Impact of the Regulatory Push ON CONCLUSIONS

The goal of *retex.green* (2022), the first national producers' consortium for the efficient management of waste from clothing, textiles, footwear, and leather goods in Italy, was to make the Fashion System circular at last, anticipate legislative decisions regarding textile recycling, and offer a useful operational tool for all supply chain participants. In addition to the possibility that the individual producer lacks the organizational capability required to manage the garbage he produces, the economics of waste management can be extremely expensive if tactics that yield financial gains are not implemented. Therefore, the Collective System would significantly improve waste valorization by offering a workable substitute.

The Italian deadline for delivering the decree governing the end-of-life of textile waste (textile EPR) to the Minister of Environment and Energy Security (MASE) ended in April 2023. Under this rule, the actual end-of-life managers of goods put on the market will be textile importers and producers. They will be alone in charge of organizing and funding the separate collection, recycling, recovery, and preparation of waste for reuse. In order to do this, they will need to engage with municipalities to establish a national network for collecting textile waste, develop selective collection methods, and create sustainable textile goods that can be repaired and reused. Manufacturers and distributors, who are impacted by the responsibilities of a system that is still controlled by towns and their managers,

are not enthusiastic about the legislation. Municipal institutions, on the other hand, express dissatisfaction about the new measure's severe fragmentation of collection.

A significant role was played by Euratex, a European group representing the European textile and apparel sector with its headquarters in Brussels. Euratex claims to have been the driving force behind the ReHub (2022) plan. 3.5 to 4.5 billion euros in economic, environmental, and social benefits would be obtained by the textile recycling industry from a collaborative industrial upcycling project that places textile waste and circular materials at the core of a strategy to achieve fiber-to-fiber recycling of 2.5 million tons of textile waste by 2030. "Transform Waste into Feedstock," a project funded by ReHub, intends to construct a 50,000-ton factory by 2024.

In the Prato district, the Textile Hub (2022) is being developed as part of the municipality of Prato's "Prato Circular City" plan, a project aimed at managing the district's transition to a circular economy. By connecting its cycle to that of local businesses, the Textile Hub will be able to process 34,000 tons of textile waste annually and recycle at least 94% of it (10, 11, 15).

6. Conclusion

Textile companies understand that in order to attain circularity, both self-steering and state involvement are necessary. It is unclear, therefore, what businesses should expect from their interactions and partnerships with the public sector. Certain circular measures are viewed as less urgent, and businesses appear more accustomed to using conventional, top-down tools. Businesses' varying governance requirements highlight the challenges of adopting a circular economy in the textile sector. The Circular Economy (CE) and environmental practices work better together than either approach does on its own. However, a number of obstacles can make it challenging to apply CE in this sector, including the textile industry's reliance on customer orders and the cost of transporting raw materials. To solve these challenges, the government must implement laws and policies that encourage the

textile industry to transition to circular processes (6).

The conversion to a circular economy is a process of tremendous challenges that calls for creative policy-making, teamwork, and ongoing research. We can create a more resilient, effective, and ecologically conscious world if we can take advantage of the promise of recycling and circularity rules. Governments, corporations, consumers, and academics must all commit to adopting sustainable practices and cooperate in the pursuit of a circular and regenerative future (4).

By replacing traditional chemical methods, enzymes not only minimize environmental harm but also align with the industry's shift toward greener, more efficient production.

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Their versatility and eco-friendly nature make them indispensable in the push for sustainable fashion. The broad implementation of enzyme-based technologies will be accelerated by cooperation between academic institutions, business, and regulatory agencies as well as rising consumer demand for sustainable textile products. The textile industry has the potential to transition to a more sustainable and circular economy by implementing consistent innovation in enzyme engineering, process optimization, and integration with complementary technologies. This would significantly reduce the industry's environmental impact while simultaneously improving the quality and performance of its products.

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